

Crime-Prediction using Machine Learning Algorithm: A Comparative Study

Karthika C Babu

Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
karthikababu2022b@mca.ajce.in

Sr. Elsin Chakkalackal S.H

Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
elsinchakkalackal@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract — Crime is one of the major problems facing the world today. The level of crime should be reduced by using various Machine learning strategies to protect the international community from criminal or anti-civil acts. Here Algorithm Used is a Decision tree, a Random Forest classifier, Gradient boosting Classifier. The project aims to develop crime-predicting models. The project is designed to help the FBI and police departments across the country use electronic learning to better focus their resources on crime-prone areas. The data sets used to predict crime are from Kaggle.

Keywords—crime, predict, machine learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world security is a priority for all political governments and governments around the world and aims to reduce crime. Crime is a crime that deserves to be condemned and punished by the community, usually in the form of fines or imprisonment. A crime or crime (or criminal case) is an act that not only harms an individual or people but also the community, community, or government ("public wrongdoing"). In this paper, crime guessing is done by making machine learning algorithms like decision tree, Random Forest Classifier, K-means, and Gradient Boosting Classifier on the criminal database using the Google Collab. The project is designed to help the FBI and police departments across the country use electronic learning to better focus their resources on crime-prone areas.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Lawrence McClendon et al.[1] In the communities and crime dataset, researchers utilized linear regression, additive regression, and decision algorithms with an identical set of inputs. In general, while comparing the three algorithms, the linear regression algorithm produced the best results.

Jyoti Agarwal et al. [2] developed a crime analysis challenge by using a fast crime mining tool to implement an aggregation algorithm on crime datasets and studying crime by looking at and planned murders throughout the year. A solution to this problem is devised, in which crime analysis is performed on the crime dataset utilizing the fast-mining tool and the k means aggregation approach. The combined statistics make it easy to spot crime trends over time, which can be used to develop future prevention strategies.

Vineet Jain et al. [3] have developed a solution to the problem of the system that can anticipate areas with high crime probability and can visualize crime-prone areas. They obtained the combined results using

the k-mean algorithm. Crime-prone areas are easy to detect and can be used to design precautionary techniques for fate.

Chirag Kansara et al. [4] created a model that evaluates people's emotions on Twitter and predicts whether they are a threat to a certain person or community. The Naive Bayes Classifier, which rates people based on sentiment analysis, is used to do this.

Benjamin et al. [5] Aggregation is the process of assembling the attributes and features of an element so that data objects in one set are larger than data objects in any other. But it is now a very difficult long road due to the sharp surge in the huge volume of information resulting from the use of many applications. Fixing these problems is the difficulty of much recent research work. Thus, an evaluation of k-mean clustering algorithms is conducted.

III. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to obtain a Machine Learning model to predict crime in different communities using the data provided with accuracy. Here, two databases are used such as community_crime_clean and community_crime_full. The model should be trained with additional data to obtain reading accuracy. Focuses resources in areas where crime is likely to occur. Uses Decision Trees, K means, Gradient Boosting Classifier, and Random Forests. We also did 10 folding Cross-Validation. The results are different, and we classify the results based on the metrics of different models. It can also be tested on multiple models to determine the best that can be used to predict crime rates.

The steps that require to be followed are:

1. Data Collection
2. Data Pre-processing
3. Model Building
4. Evaluate
5. Result

- A. **Data Collection:** There are 2 databases used to predict crime, the attributes of this database are used for model training. In both databases, there are approximately 1995 data samples in the database. Title columns and labels. This data is used to classify and predict the outcome.

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B. Machine Learning: This is used to help the user to predict the crime of different communities with optimum accuracy. The machine learning algorithms are used to predict high crimes, that will use the dataset given. The machine learning algorithms rely on how it is trained, the best algorithm relies on the sort of problem you're trying to solve, the computing resources you have, and the data you're working with.

- 1. Random Forest:** A random forest section creates a set of decision trees from a randomly selected small set of the training set. A set of decision trees (DT) from a randomly selected small set of the training set and Collect votes on different decision trees to determine the final forecast.
- 2. Gradient boosting Classifier:** The Gradient Boosting Classifier is an add-on for a basic model whose error is corrected by successive repetitions (or phases) with the addition of Regression Trees fixing residual (previous phase error).
- 3. Decision Tree Classifier:** The decision tree section creates a differentiated model by constructing a decision tree. Each node in the tree specifies a test on the attribute, and each branch that descends on that node corresponds to one of the possible values of that feature.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The steps involved are:

1. Import the packages

```
import pandas as pd # panda's nickname is pd
import numpy as np
import sklearn.metrics as metrics
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier, export_graphviz
from sklearn import svm
from sklearn.model_selection import cross_val_score
from sklearn.model_selection import validation_curve
from sklearn.preprocessing import binarize
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from IPython.display import Image
from sklearn.preprocessing import PolynomialFeatures
import sklearn.preprocessing as prep
import pydotplus
import math
from sklearn.model_selection import GridSearchCV
from sklearn.cluster import KMeans
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingClassifier
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.impute import SimpleImputer
imputer = SimpleImputer(missing_values=np.nan, strategy='mean')
```

2. There are 2 datasets. Importing both datasets

```
from google.colab import files
uploaded = files.upload()

Choose Files No file chosen Upload widget is only available when enable.
Saving communities-crime-clean.csv to communities-crime-clean.csv

communities_crime_df = pd.read_csv('communities-crime-clean.csv')

# Sanity test we have good data
communities_crime_df.head()
```

```
from google.colab import files
uploaded = files.upload()

Choose Files No file chosen Upload widget is only available when enable.
Saving communities-crime-full.csv to communities-crime-full.csv
```

```
# import dirty data
df_d = pd.read_csv('communities-crime-full.csv')
```

3. In both datasets, add a high-crime field and find positive and negative instances.

First dataset

```
highCrime
False    37.280482
True     62.719518
dtype: float64
-----
Percentage Positive Instance = 62.719518314099346
Percentage Negative Instance = 37.280481685900654
```

Second Dataset

```
highCrime
False    37.261785
True     62.738215
dtype: float64
-----
Percentage Positive Instance = 62.7382146439318
Percentage Negative Instance = 37.2617853560682
```

4. Finding main features using a decision tree classifier in both datasets.

First Dataset

```
Feature ranking:
The main features used for classification
Index(['PctKids2Par', 'racePctWhite', 'racePctHispanic', 'HousVacant',
       'LemasPctOfficerDrugIn'],
      dtype='object')
Top main feature is PctKids2Par
```

The top main feature is PctKids2Par because it is the split point of the tree. This feature depicts the kids with two parents.

Second Dataset

```
Feature ranking:
[44 3 5 71 39]
Index(['PctKids2Par', 'racePctWhite', 'racePctHispanic', 'HousVacant',
       'MalePctNewMarr'],
      dtype='object')
```

V. RESULT

The result shows that we have identified the most important feature of PctKids2Par from the high crime area using the decision tree. Also, we have created a model that explains what a good algorithm should be used to predict crime with good accuracy and precision using dirty data and clean data. Random Classifier performs well in terms of metrics and could be an effective model for predicting crime data.

metrics required for an overall review might be calculated (precision, recall, accuracy).

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] McClendon, Lawrence, and Natarajan Meghanathan. "Using machine learning algorithms to analyze crime data.Machine Learning and Applications: An International Journal (MLAIJ)" "Using machine learning algorithms to examine crime data." 2015
- [2] Jyoti Agarwal, Renuka Nagpal, and Rajni Sehgal: Crime Analysis using K-Means, 83(4):1-4, December 2013
- [3] Vineet Jain, Yogesh Sharma, Ayush Bhatia, and Vaibhav Arora: Crime Prediction using K-means Algorithm, April 2017 [4] Kansara, Chirag, et al."Using Big Data analytics and risk modeling, Twitter is reducing crime." 2016 International Conference on Recent Advances and Innovations in Engineering.
- [5] Reshma Ratheesh, Anita Abraham, Jubiya George, and Mrs. Jetty Benjamin: Crime Analysis using Kmeans Algorithm (2019)

```

GradientBoostingClassifier

[ ] clf = GradientBoostingClassifier()
    clf.fit(X_d, y_d)
    #dirty dataset
    acc_scores = cross_val_score(clf, X_d, y_d, cv=10, scoring='accuracy').mean()
    pre_scores = cross_val_score(clf, X_d, y_d, cv=10, scoring='precision').mean()
    rec_scores = cross_val_score(clf, X_d, y_d, cv=10, scoring='recall').mean()
    print ('Accuracy for GradientBoostingClassifier (Dirty Data) is', acc_scores)
    print ('Precision for GradientBoostingClassifier (Dirty Data) is', pre_scores)
    print ('Recall for GradientBoostingClassifier (Dirty Data) is', rec_scores)

Accuracy for GradientBoostingClassifier (Dirty Data) is 0.8375100502512502
Precision for GradientBoostingClassifier (Dirty Data) is 0.8746553496597681
Recall for GradientBoostingClassifier (Dirty Data) is 0.8640952380952381

[ ] #clean dataset
    clf.fit(X, y)
    acc_scores = cross_val_score(clf, X, y, cv=10, scoring='accuracy').mean()
    pre_scores = cross_val_score(clf, X, y, cv=10, scoring='precision').mean()
    rec_scores = cross_val_score(clf, X, y, cv=10, scoring='recall').mean()
    print ('Accuracy GradientBoostingClassifier (Clean Data) is', acc_scores)
    print ('Precision GradientBoostingClassifier (Clean Data) is', pre_scores)
    print ('Recall is GradientBoostingClassifier (Clean Data) is ', rec_scores)

Accuracy GradientBoostingClassifier (Clean Data) is 0.7987160804010101
Precision GradientBoostingClassifier (Clean Data) is 0.8502997400891069
Recall is GradientBoostingClassifier (Clean Data) is 0.8386

[ ] clf = RandomForestClassifier(random_state=100, max_depth=3)
    rf_accuracy = cross_val_score(clf, X_d, y_d, cv=10, scoring='accuracy').mean()
    rf_precision = cross_val_score(clf, X_d, y_d, cv=10, scoring='precision').mean()
    rf_recall = cross_val_score(clf, X_d, y_d, cv=10, scoring='recall').mean()

    print ('Accuracy for RandomForestClassifier is', rf_accuracy)
    print ('Precision for RandomForestClassifier is', rf_precision)
    print ('Recall for RandomForestClassifier is', rf_recall)

Accuracy for RandomForestClassifier is 0.8239773603946733
Precision for RandomForestClassifier is 0.8401511936487005
Recall for RandomForestClassifier is 0.8396888888888889

Random Classifier shows good results in terms of metrics and would be a good model to predict the crime data.
    
```


VI. CONCLUSION

The standard of living is improving due to the economic downturn growth and development of science and technology, however various social problems are also increasing rapidly, to crime is a big problem, especially. Crime cases have already taken place irreversible, and even if the criminal is punished for the crimes they commit, the pain of the victim and their family cannot be cured. This project focuses on crime prediction by implementing a machine learning algorithm on crime datasets using the Google Collab tool. Here 2 datasets are used. It focuses its resources on locations where crimes are more likely to be committed. From there, the basic